

White Paper

Task Force 4: Cross-cutting issues: Business & Finance, data, education & upskilling

Topic A : Financing and business models

Revision: V3

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Executive summary

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces investigating issues related to smart buildings: their objective is to identify the remaining challenges and barriers to smart building deployment, and the associated research and innovation gaps that should be addressed in the near future.

*Task force 4 (“Cross-cutting issues”) addresses the transversal requirements (Business & Finance, data, education & upskilling) to support the market uptake of smart buildings, and the strengthening of the related ecosystem. The first topic addressed by this task force and presented in this paper is **Financing and business models**.*

Smart building solutions are a strong leverage for increased energy efficiency in buildings, improved quality of life for occupants and added value for work performance. However, innovative business models and smart financing mechanisms are required to support and accelerate the ‘smartening’ of the EU building stock, which is not happening at the required pace to reach the EU goal of climate neutrality.

This white paper therefore aims to provide an overview on what is known and what should be further investigated to answer the following questions:

- Innovative business models to finance the roll-out and operation of Smart Building solutions have already been demonstrated, but their replication is very slow: how can this replication be supported?
- Smart technologies can trigger new business opportunities and revenue streams for upgraded, innovative energy services which valorise energy savings and flexible consumption and generation: how can this key enabling role be fostered?

In its first part, this paper provides a state of the art regarding the following issues, specific attention being paid to EC-funded projects:

- Existing innovative business models: A variety of business models for the smartening of the building stock exist today (both for existing and for new buildings), and more are being developed by R&D projects and market actors. However, they have so far mostly focussed on energy efficient renovation and less on making buildings smart(ready)
- Business model innovation: the majority of the new business models focus on experience and offering. The concept of “product as a service”, the integration of co-benefits (well-being) and the development of partnerships with a co-creation process are examples of such innovations
- Stakeholders’ involvement and business model co-creation: In co-created business modelling, stakeholders ideate together outside their traditional boundaries and experiment with value propositions, thereby facilitating market success.

A brainstorming process enabled to identify some key barriers and drivers regarding the development and implementation of smart financing and business models. The next diagrams provide an overview of the main barriers and drivers discussed.

Figure 1: Overview of main barriers

Figure 2: Overview of main drivers

Based on the State of the Art and the barriers and drivers, a number of research and innovation gaps were identified. They are synthesised in the next diagrams (the framed ones are those that were identified as priorities in the last meeting with the Task Force members). The topics of data ownership and privacy as well as cyber security will be further investigated in the Topic B of the Task Force.

<p>R&D</p>	<p>Develop & demonstrate new business models along the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global contract binding all stakeholders to the targeted performance - 'dynamic contract' based on performance as well on the usage values (e.g. comfort) • Financing and new models of ownership (e.g. Building as a service) for high performance buildings, especially for renovation: modular, easy replacement, upgrade, renting options • Flexible smartness to make smart buildings more affordable: a model where a user/decision maker starts with a basic platforms and adds on functionalities (sensors, etc.) according to needs. <p>Develop new business models enabled by innovative technologies such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blockchain and tokenisation: transfer know-how from the energy sector • Buildings as virtual power plants <p>Create a common Smart Building assessment framework: how to “sell & package” Smart Buildings? What is the ‘best’ business model depending on the type of building and type of user?</p>
<p>DEMO</p>	<p>Develop and maintain an Open EU database on costs and savings (Database of demonstrations/showcases with clear cost breakdown before/after measurements, financing, etc.</p> <p>Demos of innovative business models with social housing as springboard market</p> <p>Demonstrate a BM combining Internet access with other services such as energy monitoring & management or assisted living</p>

Figure 3: R&I gaps

<p>REGULATION & LEGAL FRAMEWORK</p>	<p>Initiate a European regulation for the deployment of universal digital infrastructure (with internet access as the basis) in every building within the next 5 years:</p> <p>Launch (or sustain) “Positive” national or local regulations, which support the smartening of buildings thanks to subsidies, tax reduction, etc.</p>
<p>CERTIFICATION & STANDARDISATION</p>	<p>Roll out the SRI in EU Member States</p> <p>Investigate the additional value of a smart certified building</p> <p>Develop Green Building certifications for Smart Building (e.g. adaptation of LEED / BREEAM)</p>
<p>SCALING UP & INDUSTRIALISATION</p>	<p>Provide smart lots in public procurement, i.e. earmark specific lots to building smartness and performance, to make sure this is correctly addressed by the contractors</p> <p>Promote green public procurement to support its uptake for smartening buildings, or develop incentives/subsidies and/or tax reduction based on e.g. energy efficiency</p> <p>Provide convincing and detailed use cases: presentation of examples where the business case was clear & worked well, to make stakeholders aware of them</p>
<p>UPSKILLING & AWARENESS RAISING</p>	<p>Develop upskilling/ training programmes for local contractors to involve them in performance-based business models (and also to make business model design more accessible) – <i>To be further addressed in Task Force 4 / topic C</i></p>

Figure 4: “Go-to-market’ gaps

The ‘gaps’ identified above will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on smart buildings that will be produced by the SmartBuilt4EU consortium by mid-2023, together with some recommendations targeting policy makers.

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List of abbreviations

aaS	As a Service
AEPC	Active Building Energy Performance Contracting
BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
BIM	and Building Information Modelling
BM	Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
BMS	Building Management Systems
DR	Demand Response
DSM	Demand Side Management
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Contracts
ESCO	Energy Service Company
eVs	Electric Vehicles
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEQ	Indoor Environment Quality
OSS	One Stop shop
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TF	Task Force

1. Introduction

This white paper is produced in the context of the SmartBuilt4EU project, a coordination and support action funded by the European Commission to bring together the research and innovation community on smart buildings.

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces with volunteers all across Europe, investigating topics related to smart buildings. They respectively address the interaction between building and end-user, efficient building operation, interactions between the building and the external environment, and cross cutting issues.

Figure 5: The four Task Forces set up by the SmartBuilt4EU project

SmartBuilt4EU task force 4 (“Cross-cutting issues”) addresses the transversal requirements (Business & Finance, data, education & upskilling) to support the market uptake of smart buildings, and the strengthening of the related ecosystem.

The Task Force will focus on 3 topics (one per semester):

- **Topic A: Smart financing & business models:** New services and business models (incl. Building as a Service), integration of new enabling technologies for innovative business models (e.g. blockchain)
- **Topic B: Data governance:** Data ownership and accessibility, regulations protecting the consumer; Cyber-security; Data privacy & protection (*this topic will be highly connected to Interoperability in TF2*)
- **Topic C: Education and upskilling:** Better integration of topics related to smart buildings (e.g. smart solutions & user-centric dimensions) in curricula of academic and vocational education; upskilling and training of the building value chain, support to the evolution of businesses (getting digital)

The present White Paper focusses on the first topic, i.e. “**Smart financing & business models**”. It presents the outcomes of a collective work, carried out with the members of the Task Forces, in several steps:

- Agreement on the scope
- Review of the State of the Art and identification of the points to be investigated in particular
- Analysis of barriers and drivers
- Identification of R&I gaps

2. Topic under investigation by the Task Force

2.1. Rationale

Innovative business models and smart financing mechanisms are required to support and accelerate the ‘smartening’ of the EU building stock. With a staggering 97%¹ of the building stock estimated as being energy inefficient, the building sector indeed plays a key role for achieving Europe’s goal of climate neutrality by 2050. In addition to conventional renovation measures (e.g. thermal insulation of the building envelope), smart digital technologies can be instrumental to reach this potential. Thanks to the advancements in sensors, controllers and communication technologies, buildings can be transformed from passive isolated elements to smart-ready buildings with optimal control, fully integrated to the energy system and other infrastructures, while answering occupants’ needs. Achieving this transformation requires a significant increase in deployment of energy efficient measures in buildings and homes, that increase both the level of “smartness” of the building as well as the depth of renovation. However, the ‘smartening’ and energy efficient renovation of the building stock is not happening at the required pace (at least 3%) needed for Europe to reach its goal of climate neutrality.

This white paper therefore aims to provide an overview on what is known and what should be further investigated to answer the following questions:

- Innovative business models to finance the roll-out and operation of Smart Building solutions have already been demonstrated, but their replication is very slow: how can this replication be supported?
- Smart technologies can trigger new business opportunities and revenue streams for upgraded, innovative energy services which valorise energy savings and flexible consumption and generation: how can this key enabling role be fostered?

2.2. Scope

The purpose of this section is to define the scope of the topic being investigated. Potential interactions with other topics addressed by the different SmartBuilt4EU Task Forces are also clarified.

The following ‘blocks of knowledge’ were identified during the 1st meeting of the Task Force:

- **Existing Innovative Business models:** A variety of innovative Business Models (BM) for the smartening of the building stock exist today (both for existing and for new buildings), and more are being developed by R&D projects and market actors. Among them, Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs) were perceived as a key type of business model (provided they are successfully transferred to the residential sector and private homes, and/or become more commercially viable thanks to ‘enhanced’ functionalities such as Demand Response). More generally, “Product as a service” BMs were deemed as very relevant (e.g. Building as a Service; Verticals for building as a service

¹ According to a study conducted by BPIE, 97% of European buildings are energy-inefficient, meaning they must be upgraded to comply with the 2050 vision of decarbonisation. This figure is much higher than the 75% previously estimated.

- heating as a service, ventilation as a service, cooling as a service, technical monitoring as a service; BIM as a Service; Building Management System as a Service; Cyber Security as a Service; service models for smart technologies including repair, continuous software improvements, etc.). Enablers of emerging BMs such as blockchain for smart energy contracts or SRI for in-use building performance as a service were also mentioned.
- **Business model innovation** for the development of new business models or the improvement of existing ones: there was a consensus that we need to go beyond the CAPEX rationale which is the rule today, by implementing a total cost approach as well as including co-benefits (social & environmental). New business models should also account for the need of increased building resilience (to climate change, pandemics, etc) and flexibility (i.e. ability to answer to rapidly changing societal needs).
- **Stakeholders' involvement:** For BM innovation to deliver successful business models that can quickly be rolled out, it is critical to ensure that business models are user-centric and co-created with stakeholders. This requires for instance identifying value proposition for each stakeholder/ organisation in the value chain, understanding their pains & gains, and finding ways to better involve stakeholders in the buildings' lifetime.
- **Support to the market uptake of innovative business models:** so as to promote successful business models, we need concrete use cases describing the business models & quantifying the added value, as well as meaningful metrics to communicate to decision makers and relevant stakeholders.

The scope of the « Financing & business models » topic to be investigated by the Task Force can be synthesised as:

- Innovative business models to be promoted
- How to improve existing business models or develop new ones (*e.g. user-centric business model, total cost approach, integration of co-benefits, integration of resilience and flexibility*)
- How to better engage with all stakeholders of the value chain of Smart Buildings
- How to support the market take-up of innovative business models

3. State of the Art

3.1. Foreword

Business models being the focus of this first White Paper, Business Model Canvases will be mentioned or used several times in this document. The most commonly used BMC today is Osterwalder’s², however a simplified version (adapted from Gassmann et al. (2014)) might also be used in this document – as illustrated on the right.

3.2. Literature review

3.2.1. Synthesis

Innovative business models to smarten the building stock have already been developed and demonstrated by market players or in the framework of publicly funded projects (Table 1). Several EU-funded projects (see Figure 9) are investigating and developing innovative business models to make buildings smarter and more efficient. However, they have so far mostly focussed on energy efficient renovation and less on making buildings smart(ready).

According to the H2020 STUNNING³ project, business model patterns can be categorised in four main families: based on One Stop Shop concept, based on Product Service Systems (“product as a service”, ESCOs), based on innovative financing schemes, based on new revenue models. Real business models are often a combination of several business model patterns: combining several patterns can provide a more robust business model. The project also identified **One Stop shops (OSSs)** and **Energy Performance Contracting (EPCs)** as one of the most efficient models for bringing energy renovations to market.

In H2020 funded project MySMARTlife⁴, the concept of “product as a service”, the integration of co-benefits (well-being) and the development of partnerships with a co-creation process were identified as key innovations.

Enhanced Energy Performance Contracts (in some cases combined with Demand Response) are the focus of several H2020 funded projects: AMBIENCE, NOVICE, MOEEBIUS, HOLISDER to name some of them. In MOEEBIUS the incorporation of comfort and health parameters as part of an EPC, real time automation, predictive maintenance, gamification and behavioural triggering are some examples of innovative aspects that were introduced in the ESCO business models – thereby making them “smarter” than conventional EPCs.

Innovative Business Models such as **Pay-for-Performance** are also emerging (e.g. H2020 SENSEI project).

² <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas/business-model-canvas>

³ See STUNNING project

⁴ D1.9 Innovative business models. Making things happen / WP1, Task 1.2

Table 1: Synthesis of Business Models identified during the review of the State of the Art⁵

Business model pattern	Business model type	Example of project / offer where it has been implemented or tested	Status of deployment
Product as a Service	Energy Performance Contracting (EPC)		Commercial for tertiary buildings, pre-commercial for social housing, demo for residential
	Active EPC (EPC + Demand Response)		Demo
	Building as a service, heating as a service, ventilation as a service, cooling as a service, BMS as a service (BMaaS), etc	Lenheat (Danfoss – Heat as a service), halcyon cloudBMS (PhotonStar - BMaaS), etc.	Commercial for tertiary buildings, demo for residential
	Energy Supply Contracting (ESC)	Provided by energy utilities	Commercial for tertiary
	Integrated Energy Contracting (IEC)	Provided by energy utilities	Commercial for tertiary
One Stop Shop (OSS) (focussing on energy efficient renovation for now)	OSS provided as a complementary business (e.g. by utilities)	Examples from utilities	Commercial
	OSS provided by PPP and semi-public entities		Commercial
	OSS provided by joint venture of retailers with industry and contractors		Commercial
	OSS provided by contractors' cluster cooperation		Commercial
	OSS supported by digital tools		Commercial
	OSS supported by a Step-by-Step approach		Demo
Innovative financing scheme (focussing on energy efficient renovation for now)	Home-based financing		Demo
	On-bill financing	Already provided by some energy utilities to finance PV	Commercial
	Energy savings obligations	Provided by many energy utilities	Commercial
	Crowdfunding		Only few examples
New revenue models	Pay-for-Performance / Provision of flexibility services to the grid		Demo
	Building owner benefiting from rent increase thanks to improved smartness		For tertiary buildings mainly
	Increase of property value thanks to labels and certification		For non-residential buildings

⁵ Please note that most of these BM are not specifically for smart buildings, but rather for conventional renovation approaches

3.2.2. Business model innovation

In MySMARTlife⁶, business model innovations were studied and compared in pilot interventions that took place in three lighthouse cities: Nantes, Hamburg, and Helsinki. The BM innovations were categorised according to their **type** (configuration, offering or experience⁷) and **degree** (incremental, lateral, disruptive). The report concluded that the majority of the new business models focussed on experience and offering, and came from an incremental innovation process, which means that they try to take advantage of previous products/services already in the market. **The concept of “product as a service”, the integration of co-benefits (well-being) and the development of partnerships with a co-creation process were identified as key innovations.**

Figure 6: Basic features of a Business Model innovation (Source: mySMARTLife D1.9, Adapted from Keeley et al., 2013)

In the **STUNNING project**, several recommendations on business model innovation were derived from exchanges with stakeholders and with other EU projects. For each BM component, the following recommendations were given:

⁶ D1.9 Innovative business models. Making things happen / WP1, Task 1.2

⁷ Keeley, L., Walters, H., Pikkell, R., & Quinn, B. (2013): Ten Types of innovation: The Discipline of Building Breakthroughs. New York: Wiley

Figure 7: Recommendations for BM innovation for the energy efficient renovation of buildings (Source: STUNNING, 2019)

3.2.3. Stakeholders’ involvement and business model co-creation

Technological advances, disruptive changes and economic shifts are rapidly rendering traditional business models obsolete. To anchor co-created business models (co-innovation) in a wider setting of new business models: performance, incubator, co-innovation, ecosystem, (Blasberg, 2021) it will definitely occupy the co-innovation space and possibly draw from other philosophies, depending on the stakeholders themselves. Strategy formulation in the co-creation paradigm begins with a focus on the entire ecosystem, and imagines and drafts a new value chain that benefits all participants, agents and stakeholders. In this way it follows the principle of efficiency as defined by maximizing the size of the pie as opposed to maximizing a single firm’s or agent’s slice of the pie (Ramaswamy and Gouillart, 2010). Therefore, business models with co-innovation value are rooted in mutual benefit. Many business models for innovative technologies do not achieve market success because they do not address the problem of misaligned incentives and because their structure does not distribute, and therefore lower, risks during implementation (Blasberg, 2021). In co-created business modelling stakeholders ideate together outside their traditional boundaries and experiment with value propositions.

Business model co-creation also has a flavour of ecosystem approach as the future of complex ecosystem such as smart cities and smart buildings depends on boundary-spanning business model innovation.

Figure 8: A generic BM co-creation approach

The best way to co-create value is to focus on the experiences of all stakeholders and to this end take them across the entire co-creation process, starting co-diagnostics, moving to co-design and co-implementation, to complete with co-evaluation (for details see Figure 8). Co-creation ecosystems in their nature are based multi-stakeholder engagement and cannot exist without it, and therefore mapping the relevant ecosystem participants is key. They are non-standard, diverse in scale, process, goals and various other parameters. *They re-configure society around a new set of technologies* (Engels et al., 2018) but they are also quite rare. While there is an increasing number of attempts through living labs and applying co-creation in various H2020 projects, a true and wide sharing of objective setting and decision-making power with the stakeholders is not a frequent approach. Possible reasons behind this include inertia, uncertain or untested benefits and the risk of losing control over the process in terms of economic cost and implementation time.

3.3. Lessons learnt from H2020 projects

3.3.1. Overview

Many H2020 projects have reviewed, developed and/or demonstrated new business model: some of them are pictured in Figure 9. Although it is likely that this list is not exhaustive, it covers the projects represented (or mentioned) in the Task Force.

Figure 9: Relevant H2020 projects identified by the Task Force members

Key lessons learnt or conclusions from some of these projects have already been presented in the state of the art. We will now dive deeper in the lessons learnt from a few selected projects.

3.3.2. Lessons learnt from the Ambience project

Actively Managed Buildings with Energy Performance Contracting ([Ambience](#)) - is an H2020 project that aims to extend the concept of energy performance contracting (EPC) for active building and making the model available and attractive to a wider range of building typologies.

In the generic Active Building EPC (AEPC) Business Model, an ESCO delivers an AEPC service, consisting of guaranteed energy cost savings - based on energy efficiency and (renewable) energy supply measures and active control of flexibility – to an end customer. In case of classic EPC, it is energy savings (kWh) that are being guaranteed and they are typically multiplied by a contractually agreed (average) energy price. This is done for each energy vector (electricity, gas, fuel, etc.). In the case of AEPC, because of the more dynamic pricing, the business model is about providing cost savings. These cost savings will come partially from energy efficiency, partially from flexibility, but in particular the flexibility contribution will aim at delivering cost savings, not necessarily energy savings. The way to measure these cost savings will thus also differ from the pure energy consumption savings. Underlying CO2 savings will in both cases be a secondary or even primary driver. Active control of the flexibility is a key factor of AEPC. Without it, we cannot consider it as an AEPC model.

Lessons learned so far include:

- Active building energy performance contracting potential depends heavily on the initial situations of the building and what measures are being implemented,
- Influenced by the level of dynamic pricing available with demand response (this has taken years in some countries)⁸
 - o Demand response services vary widely by country
 - o EPC market maturity varies by country
- Early simulations have shown that for a residential building, there is a potential improvement of around 5-20% expressed in terms of total cost of ownership and benefits lasting over 25-30 years

3.3.3. Lessons learnt from the TABEDE project

TABEDE (completed in April 2021) aimed to allow all buildings equipped with Building Management Systems (BMS) to integrate energy grid demand response (DR) schemes, independently of communication protocols. The overarching objectives were to develop a highly interoperable system that maximizes building flexibility with energy cost savings validated in real buildings.

Lessons learned & recommendations for Demand Response BM include:

- **For European policy makers:**
 - o Ensure adequate remuneration for end-users to participate in DR schemes
 - o Facilitate business model innovation to allow DSOs to partake in the benefits of building-level flexibility
- **For Green/ Smart building rating organisations:**
 - o Require a minimum SRI score for all buildings upgraded through the Green Deal's Renovation Wave
 - o Incorporate appliance "smartness" in the EU's energy labelling system

⁸ An analysis has been done and can be found [here](#)

3.3.4. Lessons learnt from the HOLISDER project

HOLISDER (completed in March 2021) brought together a wide range of mature technologies and integrated them in an open and interoperable framework, comprising in a fully-fledged suite of tools addressing the needs of the whole demand response value chain. The objective was to ensure consumer empowerment and transformation into active market players, through the deployment of a variety of implicit and hybrid demand response schemes, supported by a variety of end-user applications for Personalized Informative Billing, Human-Centric Energy Management, Load Scheduling and Intelligent Controls, Self-consumption promotion and cost-effective storage, Predictive Maintenance, along with Context-Aware Automation.

Lessons learned include:

- The development of **brand-agnostic services** is complicated by the multitude of in-house and "walled garden" approach of some of the equipment manufacturers.
- The **automatic configuration of residential equipment** would enable broader access to demand-side flexibility services.
- **Blockchain technology** may become the critical additional ingredient that will **unlock the new business models**.

4. Barriers and drivers

4.1. Barriers

Barriers to the market uptake of smart buildings (and the strengthening of the related ecosystem) related to business models and financing were reviewed and prioritised by the Task Forces. The top barriers are highlighted below; all were related to the value chain.

VALUE CHAIN	Silo and corporatist thinking and acting, no efficient use of ecosystems	<i>Top barriers according to the Task Force</i>
	Lack of skills & training, cultural gap of many decision makers who are too often digital technology adverse or ignorant	
	Lack of understanding of new business models within value chain stakeholders, reluctance to change long lasting corporate business models	
	Construction industry too far away from final users of buildings – i.e. driven by financial & regulatory considerations, not user value considerations	
REGULATION	Lack of continuity in national regulations (in particular for incentives)	
SOCIAL	Lack of knowledge especially from building owners side	
	Decision-making inertia of building professionals and building owners/ tenants	
	Difficulties in conveying the non-energy benefits	
	Lack of trust in the final performance and quality	
	Reluctance to use the latest technologies	
ECONOMIC	"Lowest cost" mindset, based on CAPEX, with no total cost approach	
	Limited financing options, and limited third-party financing involvement	
	Split incentives and conflicts of interest: Benefits and investments are not done by the same stakeholder	

4.2. Drivers

The drivers identified by the Task Force are as illustrated below. The strongest driver (according to the Task Forces member) is related to regulation.

VALUE CHAIN	New market players: ESCOs, entities providing One Stop Shops, etc.	<i>Top drivers according to the Task Force</i>
REGULATION	EU Regulation: EPBD, SRI, DIGITAL LOGBOOK and RENOVATION PASSPORT	
	Renovation Wave	
SOCIAL	Evolution of human activities, new usages	
	Ageing of population, new ways of living	
	Great appetite from consumers in general for new digital technologies	
ECONOMIC	Needs and expectations of people on actual/contextual building performance aspects (e.g. energy, costs, environment, IEQ)	
	Good practices from projects and initiatives implementing business models overcoming the upfront financing issue (e.g. EPCs, home based financing, etc.)	
TECHNICAL	Innovation / technological enablers for new business models: e.g. blockchain enabling smart contracts	

5. Gaps

Various activities required to overcome the barriers and leverage the drivers (related to smart financing and business models) were suggested and prioritised by the Task Force members (Table 2). The priority ones according to the Task Force are in bold.

Table 2: Suggested R&I activities

Type of activity	Activities
R&D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop & demonstrate new business models along the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Global contract linking/ binding all stakeholders to the targeted performance - 'dynamic contract' based on performance as well on the usage values (e.g. comfort) ○ Financing and new models of ownership (e.g. Building as a service) for high performance buildings, especially for renovation: modular, easy replacement, upgrade, renting options ○ Flexible smartness to make smart buildings more affordable: a model where a user/decision maker starts with a basic platforms and adds on functionalities (sensors, etc.) according to needs. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ How can the fixed starting cost be rebalanced with marginal cost of extra appliances? (BM research needed). ▪ Integration of cybersecurity and data privacy concerns into flexible/modular design ○ Using innovative technologies & approach such as blockchain and tokenisation: transfer know-how from the energy sector ○ Buildings as virtual power plants - Create a common Smart Building assessment framework: how to “sell & package” SB best? What is the ‘best’ business model depending on the type of building and type of user?
Demonstration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and maintain an Open EU database on costs and savings: Database of demonstrations/ showcases with clear cost breakdown and explaining how they were financed, along with objectives (desired outcomes), before/after measurements, user types, building type, local context (from culture to climate), etc., as well as a standardized format for all this data for comparability - Demos of innovative business models with social housing as springboard market - Demonstrate a BM combining Internet access with other services such as energy monitoring & management or assisted living
Regulation & legal framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initiate a European regulation for the deployment of universal digital infrastructure (with internet access as the basis) in every building within the next 5 years: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ setting high targets and enabling/ supporting innovation ○ promoting transversal approach that pool digital infrastructures / provide multiple services (e.g. energy efficiency, assisted living) - Launch (or maintain) “Positive” national or local regulations, which support the smartening of buildings thanks to subsidies, tax reduction, etc.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ See for instance Renolution in Brussels / Leuven Klimaatneutraal in Leuven: can provide subsidies to compensate the cost of appliances when renovating buildings ○ Tax reduction, easier obtention of building permit for smart/ high performing buildings
Certification & standardisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Roll out the SRI in EU Member States - Develop Green Building certifications for Smart Building (e.g. adaptation of LEED / BREEAM) - Investigate the additional value of a smart certified building
Scaling up & industrialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide smart lots in public procurement, i.e. earmark specific lots to building smartness and performance, to make sure this is correctly addressed by the contractors - Develop upskilling/ training programmes for local contractors to involve them in performance-based business models (and also to make business model design more accessible) – <i>To be further addressed in Task Force 4 / topic C</i> - Promote green public procurement to support its uptake for smartening buildings, or develop incentives/subsidies and/or tax reduction based on SB related energy efficiency (and other impact for example resource efficiency, improvement of indoor environment) - Provide convincing and detailed use cases: presentation of examples where the business case was clear & worked well, to make stakeholders aware of them

6. Conclusion

This document formalises the collaborative work performed by the members of SmartBuilt4EU task force 4, on a voluntary basis, during the period March - June 2021. It also integrates the feedback collected during 1) a peer review conducted by VITO in June 2021, and 2) an open consultation process during in July – August 2021.

Based on an analysis of the state of the art and the identification of barriers and drivers, the main objective of this paper is to detect some Research and Innovation gaps that still need to be addressed in the coming years in order to provide the required business models and smart financing schemes to support the market uptake of smart buildings and the smartening of existing buildings.

This White Paper will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda that the SmartBuilt4EU consortium will present to the European Commission.

Task Force 4 will investigate two more topics during 2021 – 2022: next topic, starting October 2021, will focus on **Data ownership, privacy and governance**, i.e. it will address key issues such as data sharing, data flow and security, data ownership, transparency, data governance, data security and cybersecurity.

If you have some expertise to share on this topic, you are invited to join the task force and contribute to the next White Paper (contact detail below).

To receive the updates on the SmartBuil4EU task forces, White Papers and events, please register here:
<https://smartbuilt4eu.eu/join-our-community/>

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8. Annex 1: list of H2020 projects reviewed

Table 3: list of relevant EU projects

Project	Status	Weblink	Relevant inputs
Innovative business models			
ambience	Ongoing	https://ambience-project.eu/	The project aims at extending the concept of Energy Performance Contracting to Active Buildings and making it available and attractive to a wider range of buildings.
HOLISDER	completed	http://holisder.eu/reports/	Review of “ Emerging Business Models ” for Demand Response Management (for aggregators, retailers and ESCOs), Contract templates
NOVICE	completed	http://novice-project.eu/	new business model in building renovation to better monetize energy efficiency by consolidating services and subsequent revenue streams from both energy savings (EPC) and demand response.
MOEBIUS	completed	https://www.moebius.eu/	Proposal of four innovative ESCO business models and three innovative Demand Response (DR) business models.
sensei	Ongoing	https://senseih2020.eu	Innovative pay-for-performance (P4P) schemes , where payments for energy efficiency are based on proven and measured savings in real time
TABEDE Towards buildings ready for Demand Response	completed	http://www.tabede.eu/	Demand response schemes thanks to a low cost extender for BMS systems or as standalone system
CREATORS	Ongoing	https://www.creators4you.energy/	“ CES-as-a-service ” models to support the initiation, planning, implementation and operation of Community Energy Systems
Smart financing			
EeMAP Energy efficient Mortgages Action Plan	completed	https://eemap.energyefficiencyandclimate.eu/ntmortgages.eu/	Standardised “ energy efficient mortgage ”, according to which building owners are incentivised to improve the energy efficiency of their buildings or acquire an already energy efficient property by way of preferential financing conditions linked to the mortgage
EEnvest	Ongoing	http://www.eenest.eu/	Creation of a web-based search and match platform which investors can use to evaluate the risk of investment in energy efficiency for buildings. It uses a blockchain-based data exchange validation system in order to guarantee the security and quality of the information, and a combination of technical-financial due-diligence mechanisms.
New generation Energy Performance Certificate			
ALDREN Alliance for Deep RENovation in buildings	completed	https://aldren.eu/	Voluntary certification scheme with building value evaluation from a risk investments

			calculations from renovation roadmap of building renovation passport (offices and hotels)
	Ongoing	https://epcrecast.wordpress.com/	The EPC RECAST approach is focused on the cross-exploitation of building expert knowledge, international standards for the assessment of building energy performance (ISO/CEN, Mandate M/480), smart building technology, available digital BIM technologies and workflows, data sets and inverse modelling.
	Ongoing	https://u-certproject.eu/	Introduces an Energy Performance Assessment and Certification Scheme to value buildings in a holistic and cost-effective manner
Smart City Projects			
	completed	http://www.cityfied.eu	EPC business model tested in Laguna de Duero (Torrelago district) for a residential building block
	Ongoing	https://www.mysmartlife.eu/	Review and categorisation of 12 business model innovations , and investment mechanisms for innovative business models